

SECURITY ASSESSMENT OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS AND SECURITY AWARENESS FOR INFORMATION SYSTEMS BY MALWARE ANALYSIS**Moh Moh**Faculty of Information Science Department, University of Computer Studies (Mandalay)
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ABSTRACT

Security analysis is the process of deciding which securities are sound investments. True investments keep the principal safe and deliver an acceptable return. Any purchase mobile applications that does not meet these criteria is speculation. This paper outcome display security assessment and analysis of mobile application for developers can identify security features which were not found to be up to mark based on the reviews, and thus work upon them to deliver better applications. Next point objective is the awareness of information security awareness is to take the message to the people who stakeholder's in information systems.

KEYWORDS:

Mobile Applications, Malware, Assessment, Analysis, Exploitation, Threats, Integrity, Availability, Confidentiality

INTRODUCTION

Information security is protecting information and information system from unauthorized access, use, disclosure, disclosure, disruption, modification or destruction in order to provide confidentiality, integrity and availability. It is a major issue for businesses information system. Confidentiality: means preserving authorized restrictions on access and disclosure, including means for protecting personal privacy and proprietary information. Integrity: means guarding against improper information modification or destruction, and includes ensuring information non-repudiation and authenticity. Availability: means ensuring timely and reliable access to and use of information.

Information Security four major Components and different types

Four major components are

1. Assets, 2. Vulnerability, 3. Threat and 4. Control

Different security types are:

- 1). Organization and infrastructure security
- 2). Policy, standards and procedures security
- 3). Baselines and risk assessments security
- 4). Awareness and training program security
- 5). Compliance security.

Security Requirements: Needs for information systems security and trust can be formulated in terms of several major Requirements:

- Data confidentiality
- Data integrity
- System availability
- Resources
- System configuration
- Authentication
- Authorization
- Auditing
- non-repudiation

The mobile application penetration testing methodology focuses on security analysis and it has been long considered that the end user is in control of the device. In this article, we shall provide an overview of this methodology and discuss its four main stages.

- 1) Discovery
- 2) Assessment /Analysis
- 3) Exploitation
- 4) Reporting

WORK PLAN

In this section, we present step by step procedure of work plan.

- (1) Searched and downloaded sample Myanmar Mobile Applications and sample of business information
- (2) Collected a set of applications based on (attributes and a particular feature)
- (3) Select Methods and search APK tools for security test with inclusive malware analysis.
- (4) Experimental results
- (6) Finally, Analysis report and awareness of security assessment results and display to message.

EVALUATION METHODOLOGIES AND APPLY AUTOMATIC TOOLS

There are millions of mobile apps are available in market. But, most of the mobile users first prefer high ranked apps when downloading it. If the user wants to download application, to visit play store such as Google Play Store, Apples store etc. When users visit to play-store application, then he or she is able to see the various application lists. This list is built on the basis of promotion or advertisement. User doesn't have knowledge about the application (i.e. which applications are useful or useless). So user looks at the list and downloads the applications. But sometimes it happens that the downloaded application won't work or not useful. To avoid this, we are making application in which we are going to list the applications.

Table 1. Collected a set of applications based on (attributes and a particular feature) tools analysis report

App Name	Login	Sensitive Info:	Confidential Info:	Financial
Buddhan	N	N	N	N
Doe Taung Thu	N	N	N	N
Hlwint Live	Y	Y	Y	N
iZayCho	Y	Y	Y	Y
MMEarn	Y	Y	Y	Y
Mom's talk	Y	Y	Y	N
Phoosar	Y	Y	Y	N
....				
.....				

METHODOLOGIES

In our system, some methodologies are used for security testing.

M1-Improper Platform Usage

- Check for permission apply to Apktool
- Check for permission from Google Playstore
- Check for permission apply to Drozer Module

M2-Insecure Data Storage

- Search for unencrypted user credentials
- Retrieve data from Database
- Search data from Temp file
- Search data as (file -type) from External Storage
- Search data from log

M3-Insecure Communication

- Check security feature to Burp Suite and Traffic
- SSL Certificate Printing Technique By Pass

M4-Insecure Authentication

- Check session Management

M5-Insufficient Cryptography

- Checking in secure cryptography implementation

M6-Insecure Authorization

- Use Activity apply adb shell
- Check Content Provider
- Receiver Exported Checking and By Pass Technique

M9-Reverse Engineering

- Hardcoded Issue
- Hardcoded issue in native library file

APK Tools

Some of the security APK tools are described in the following figure.

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Name	Date modified	Type	Size
apk_files	5/29/2018 10:09 AM	File folder	
7z1801-x64.exe	2/21/2018 4:43 PM	Application	1,382 KB
7z1805.exe	5/22/2018 5:05 PM	Application	1,154 KB
burpsuite_community_windows-x64_v1_...	5/28/2018 5:21 PM	Application	92,201 KB
cmdcr.zip	5/10/2018 4:57 PM	WinRAR ZIP archive	102,824 KB
drozer-2.4.4.win32.7z	5/18/2018 12:48 AM	WinRAR archive	27,552 KB
Genymotion.7z	5/18/2018 12:47 AM	WinRAR archive	603,170 KB
genymotion_vbox66p_51_170938_222241...	5/29/2018 1:13 PM	OVA File	254,630 KB
Genymotion-ARM-Translation_v1.1.zip	3/5/2018 11:38 AM	WinRAR ZIP archive	9,171 KB
jadx.7z	5/18/2018 12:46 AM	WinRAR archive	3,663 KB
ID-GUI.7z	5/18/2018 12:46 AM	WinRAR archive	7,584 KB
jdk-8u171-windows-586.7z	5/22/2018 5:07 PM	WinRAR archive	201,754 KB
jdk-8u171-windows-586.exe	5/22/2018 5:06 PM	Application	203,878 KB
jdk-8u172-windows-x64.7z	5/18/2018 12:49 AM	WinRAR archive	209,936 KB
note.md	5/18/2018 1:21 AM	MD File	2 KB
npp.7.5.6.installer.x64.7z	5/18/2018 12:49 AM	WinRAR archive	4,438 KB
platform-tools.7z	5/18/2018 12:45 AM	WinRAR archive	12,634 KB
python-2.7.15.amd64.7z	5/18/2018 12:49 AM	WinRAR archive	19,132 KB

Figure 1 APK tools

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS IN TESTING FOR MOBILE APPLICATIONS

Our case study involve three hundred user’s feedback comments and sample hundred Mobile Applications and some methodologies and APK tools for security testing.

This system is analyzed the application by seven methods as shown in the following figures:

Method 1. Improper Platform Usage

Figure 2. Permission List

Method 2. Insecure Data Storage

Figure 3. Log Files

Method 3. Insecure Communication

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Figure 4. Communication and Traffic

Method 4. Insecure Authentication

Figure 5. Authentication page

Method 5. Insufficient Cryptography

Figure 6. Security page

Method 6. Insecure Authorization

Figure 7. Authorization page

Method 9. Reverse Engineering

Figure 6. Hardcoded Issue page

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS TESTING FOR BUSINESS INFORMATION SYSTEMS BY MALWARE

Fig: Malware analysis - dynamic analysis(run to <https://any.run/>)

Fig: 'Select ' Malware type

Fig: Run to start analysis and click add time,, to increase analysis time

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Fig: click text report to show result

Fig: Show Malware infected process/ registry / exe.....

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Fig: Run original exe,,, to create 2 child exe (first exe,,, is no infected malicious code)

Fig: Run Second exe is found malware code

CONCLUSION

Mobile application testing reduces risks, tests potential vulnerabilities, and examine software to ensure that an application is safe and meets adequate security compliance. Security experts use a variety of tests and strategies to monitor vulnerabilities to assess the security of a mobile application. Without through security testing, threat creators could infect your application with malware, spyware, and it could leave your user's financial account information and personal credentials exposed. Thus, this paper provides security awareness and Mobile Application users into applying the right application. This system presents analysis of Myanmar mobile applications for mobile devices that automatically discovered good security features.

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